

Travails on the New Normal Face-to-Face Classes: Views of Teachers in Baracayo Integrated School

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Abstract. This study explored the teacher's accounts of the new normal face-to-face classes. I narrowed down the highlights and lowlights of the existing issues in online learning, its effectiveness, and the teacher's coping practices on the challenges that come along the way. I used qualitative and phenomenological approaches to achieve the study's objectives. The 10 participants of this study were from Baracayo Integrated School, Division OF Davao City. I used a semi-structured online interview using the coding technique to analyze the data. In the study, the following themes revealed Increased workload: the teachers must ensure that their classrooms are secure and adhere to IATF guidelines. Another subtheme was Changes to Classroom Dynamics; Teachers' were more likely to provide kids with a clear structure and expectations for how to behave in school if they were well-prepared and confident about their ability to control classroom behavior. Another coping mechanism of the teachers was self-care and Empathy. The study further implies that collaboration between school principals is essential as it provides ways for problem-solving within the school and supports teachers' minds. Some issues would need to be addressed as schools transition back to face-to-face classes after the pandemic. Schools may need to adapt their teaching methods better to meet the needs of students in the post-pandemic world. This may include incorporating more technology into the classroom, providing flexible learning options, and incorporating experiential learning opportunities.

KEY WORDS

1. face-to-face classes 2. learning experiences 3. integrated school

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1. Introduction

Education is one of the most affected aspects of human life due to the coronavirus disease-2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. Since the rise and threat of the pandemic, many countries around the world have decided to temporarily close schools, which has affected millions of students. Consequently, students, who are mostly children, have been facing a learning crisis due to the pandemic. The challenges students encountered when face-to-face classes were implemented include a lack of instructional time and collaboration, difficulty understanding lessons and activities, and an adjustment period. Moreover, the students' main challenges with attending limited face-to-face classes were a lack of instructional time and collaboration, difficulty understanding the lessons and activities, and an adjustment period. Nevertheless, despite these challenges, they are highly motivated to keep learning in class. Education has been

the pillar of development of every country, so education is principal to the development and growth of all countries. The education system has been affected by several challenges ranging from changes in the education curriculum to closing down the education system due to widespread pandemic diseases (Owusu-Fordjour et al., 2015). COVID-19, as a public health crisis, stimulated a subsequent education crisis in which the existing achievement gap, learning loss, and dropout rate were exacerbated due to school closures (Sahu, 2020; United Nations, 2020). To prevent COVID-19 transmission, educational institutions worldwide made massive efforts to shift from in-person to online teaching (Basilaia Kvavadze, 2020; Chen et al., 2020; Daniels et al., 2021; Subedi et al., 2020). In the U.S., Schools reopening for face-to-face interactions must be carefully planned to ensure the safety of students as well as teachers and school staff in a staged fashion, especially in following physical distancing.^{7,8} Planning and execution of school health protocols during this pandemic must be supported by the truthful data being given by various institutions. Last 11 December 2020, the World Health Organization (WHO) published a checklist to support school reopening and the preparation for the possible resurgence of COVID-19.¹⁰ WHO cited that ‘The checklist is aligned with, and builds upon, existing COVID-19-related WHO guidelines and is structured around protective measures related to: hand hygiene and respiratory etiquette; physical distancing; use of masks in schools; environmental cleaning and ventilation; and respecting procedures for isolation of all people with symptoms.’ The checklist helps policymakers and school officials to enhance compliance and adherence to public health protocols during the pandemic (Sahu, 2020; United Nations, 2020). In the Philippines, the government’s Department of Education has come up with guidelines to implement online and modular distance learning delivery of instruction.

This is to safeguard students from being infected by the disease. As the COVID-19 pandemic starts to subside, Philippine schools have started to reopen. Ninety-four percent of the public schools in the Region resumed the conduct of the five-day in-person classes on November 2, more than two years since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. For many, this is a return to normality. However, teachers need to have an in-depth understanding of the “new normal”, not only in the fact that they must be primarily aware of health and social distancing, but also regarding how they frame students’ learning experience, (Garcia, 2021). The Department of Education welcomes the approval of President Rodrigo Roa Duterte and the Cabinet of the conduct of pilot face-to-face classes in very select schools within areas with low COVID-19 risk for the whole month of January 2021. The pilot will provide important experience and learning that will inform the final recommendation that DepEd intends to make on any broader resumption of face-to-face classes, (Alicia 2021). Amor (2021), DepEd emphasizes that the pilot study will be highly selective based on stringent conditions: The pilot implementation will take place only in areas categorized as low-risk (at least under Modified General Community Quarantine or MGCQ). There must be a commitment for shared responsibility of DepEd, the local government unit (LGU), and the parents or guardians. Stringent health and safety standards shall be followed at home, during travel to and from the schools, and within school premises. Ramos (2021), The Department would like to emphasize that the participation of learners in the pilot study will be voluntary, with the requisite permit issued by the parents. Face-to-face classes will not be conducted for the full week schedule. They will be under a staggered or intermittent schedule and with reduced class size to allow proper physical distancing within the classroom. Agude (2021), Regional Directors have submitted to the Secretary their nominated

schools for inclusion in the pilot study. The limited number of public schools that will participate in the pilot implementation will be determined within the month upon validation and evaluation of their compliance and readiness with respect to the risk classification, documentation of acknowledgment of shared responsibility, students and classroom management plan, and health standard requirements at home, during travel, and in school premises. Abarquez (2021), Once selected, the participating schools, LGUs, learners, and parents will undergo a thorough process of orientation, mobilization, and readiness confirmation before the actual implementation. The conduct and monitoring will be closely coordinated by the Department with the COVID-19 National Task Force (NTF). External organizations are also invited to support, give feedback, and help generate resources to ensure the success of the program. The Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) Philippines said the government's efforts in implementing full face-to-face classes have been "half-baked," citing reports received from teachers nationwide.

The researcher took the initiative to conduct a study about the teachers' travails in the new normal face-to-face classes as they were primarily the front liners in eradicating illiteracy, and it was vital that they are heard to better improve the quality of education in the new normal face to face setting. In the Davao City Division, particularly in our school, it was really quite different from before compared to this new normal setting of face-to-face classes, from the behavior of the teachers to the attitude of the learners and how they respond to the learning process. Students who exhibit flu-like symptoms were excused from in-person classes. Schools would not be held liable if a student or personnel tests positive for COVID-19. The return to face-to-face classes in the Philippines was long overdue, considering the country's education system was largely unprepared for distance learning. Studies showed students were "learning less" under the distance learning setup. Experts and lawmakers were alarmed by the learning losses brought by the pandemic.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this research study is to identify teachers' perceptions of the new normal face-to-face classes. With all the lessons learned during the COVID-19 pandemic, schools in the Philippines are more than prepared for the full implementation of face-to-face classes. No school shall be allowed to implement purely distance learning or blended learning except for those that are implementing alternative modes. Constant communication and orientation of all school community members or stakeholders must be done to ensure that everybody is aligned and fully compliant with all the health and safety protocols. That is why this study also aims to identify their coping mechanisms to address the said challenges. This is to know the different challenges that teachers experience in dealing with children in face-to-face classes.

1.2. Research Questions—The study aims to investigate teachers' perceived practice of Servant Leadership among school heads. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of the teachers in the new-normal face-to-face classes?
- (2) How did they cope with the challenges of the teachers in the new normal face-to-face classes?
- (3) What insights can be drawn from the findings of the study?

1.3. Definition of Terms—

To make this study more comprehensive, the following terms were operationally defined: New Normal Classes—The term 'new normal', which refers to online remote learning, was quickly becoming a buzzword. While the term has no definitive meaning, many have assumed it refers to more technology-driven teaching and

learning in a post-COVID context. Face-to-face classes- A face-to-face session refers to one in which participants, instructors, and facilitators meet together in the same place and at the same time. Travails- a physical or mental exertion or piece of work

1.4. Significant of the Study—The highlights of the study were significant to the following: Deped Officials- Policy/program implementers could use the results of this study to create policies and programs for teachers in able for them to help the teachers in the better implementation of the teaching and learning. Teachers were given insight into the experiences and challenges of other teachers when it comes to dealing with the learners during face-to-face classes. This would help them prepare, as they would have an idea of how

to solve problems that may occur while utilizing the approach. Stakeholders- It would help the system that must be intensively and extensively incorporated into the strategic planning of educational institutions from top management down to the lowest level of their organizational structure. Learners—help them better understand that learning must continue despite the pandemic and that it was not a hindrance to achieving educational goals. Lastly, this research would help other researchers if they wish to conduct a similar or comparative study.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This study was anchored in the psychosocial theory of education. It aims to provide teachers with psychosocial support as this was their avenue to express their struggles and challenges in the new regular face-to-face classes. Psychosocial well-being is a necessary condition for any human being to realize their full potential and to lead fulfilling, healthy, and productive lives. People with psychosocial well-being are confident, have self-esteem, feel safe, and can solve problems, make decisions, build positive social relationships, work together, and resolve conflict. Historically, education unions have insisted that quality education requires quality teachers. This is as true as ever. However, we now have a situation where teachers' expectations have increased dramatically. Teachers are expected to be agents of change, and with the pandemic, teachers are now on the front lines. At the same time, difficulties facing educational institutions

and teachers have also multiplied. All these developments have created a situation where the teacher's role is becoming more complex and demanding. Due to speedy growth and development in the entire sphere, the stress level has gone up. The teachers, staff, and administrators are in the grip of stress. Psychosocial theory addresses patterned changes in ego development, including self-understanding, identity formation, social relationships, and worldview across the lifespan. According to psychosocial theories, development refers to a product of the ongoing interactions between individuals and their social environments. The conceptual framework of the study is presented in Figure 1. As seen in the figure, there are three interconnected working themes. The Experiences of teachers to the new regular face-to-face classes, a qualitative inquiry that allows researchers and teachers to provide the necessary skills, knowledge, and focus on engaging in meaningful in-

Fig. 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study

quiry about their professional practice, would enhance this practice and effect positive changes concerning the educative goals of the learning community. There was a genuine concern, as could be viewed with the first circle, which interlinks to the second circle; however, the center

of the two circles determines that there was a connection between exploring the experiences of teachers when it comes to learning the learners was essential to the improvement of teaching and learning process for the curriculum.

2. Methodology

This chapter introduces the methods for conducting the study and gathering data. It also includes the research design, philosophical assumptions, research participants and sampling, data collection, research instrument, the trustworthiness of the study, and ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method was particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) were optimal for collecting data on individuals' personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups are influential in eliciting data on the cultural norms of a group and in generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. Patton (2002) defined phenomenology as inquiry that asks the question, "What is the structure and essence of the experience of his phenomenon for these people?" "The goal of this research worked well with this definition in trying to understand the experiences of the school heads in the new normal as they try to compare its implementation then and now. Giorgi (2007) cautioned researchers to be prepared for an investigation that was greater in both depth and breadth than the offered description implied. He suggested that information be viewed as only the tip of the iceberg.

2.1. *Philosophical Assumptions—*

The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field of study. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Decent study tasks jump within the range of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. Stanage (2007) traced the 'paradigm' back to its Greek (paradeigma) and Latin origins (paradigm), meaning pattern, model, or example. A paradigm is the patterning of a person's thinking; it is a principal example among examples, an exemplar or model to follow according to which design actions were taken. Differently stated, a paradigm was submitting to a view (Stanage, 2007). This view is supported by Denzin and Lincoln (2000), who define a research paradigm as a "basic set of beliefs that guide action", dealing with first principles, 'ultimate' or the researcher's worldview or philosophy. Ontology. This part of the research pertains to how the issue relates to the nature of reality. According to Creswell (2012), reality is subjective and multiple, as seen by participants in the study. The ontological issue addresses the nature of reality for the qualitative researcher. Reality is constructed by individuals involved in the research situation. Thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of the implementation of the curriculum in the past and the present were discussed by the participants, and their ways of coping with the implementation in the new normal are examined. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participant's answers to the study

were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the participants' responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result. The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims are justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study in order to obtain firsthand information. Guba and Lincoln (1985), as cited by Creswell (2013), state that on the epistemological assumption, the researcher attempted to lessen distance himself or herself from the participants. He suggests that, as a researcher, he or she collaborates, spends time in the field with participants, and becomes an "insider." Based on Davidson (2000) and Jones (2011). I would identify phenomenology with the use of thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers "hold explicit belief." The intention of this study is to gather information from the participants as to how they implemented the program following the guidelines set by DepEd and the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF). I assured that I would establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the teachers' experiences and coping strategies in implementing the program in the new normal. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Creswell (2013) avers that the role of values in a study is significant. Axiology suggests that the researcher openly discusses values that shape the narrative and includes their own interpretation in conjunction with the interpretation of participants. I uphold the dignity and value of every detail of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants' answers and care-

fully interpret them in light of the participants' personal interpretations. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using a personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The methodology was different from the method, and it was a creative and responsive approach to understanding questions and subject matter, while the method refers to the exact knowledge and procedure (Gerodias, 2013). In this study, the experiences of the teachers from Baracayo Integrated School, Cluster 5, Division of Davao City, were gathered through an In-Depth Interview (IDI) and their coping strategies were extracted from the participants. The researcher's inquisitiveness on the experiences of the School Heads became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which Kalof and Dietz (2008), as cited from Gerodias (2013), considered helpful in looking for "meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena." By using phenomenology, this need was hoped to be addressed by bringing the stories of the teachers in a manner that, as David (2005) wrote,

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—This study utilized a qualitative phenomenological research design. The phenomenological design describes the interpretations of the participants from their experiences. The participants were required to respond to the questions provided to them via Google Forms. Afterward, depending on the situation, they were requested to participate in a Focus Group Discussion virtually and face-to-face. At the end of this study, themes and common patterns were extracted from their responses (JamonCabanes, 2019). They decided to use a qualitative phenomenological research design because they would dwell on

definitions. In the study, the researcher used the first person to elucidate the teachers' experiences as they adopted the new mode of learning implementation amidst the pandemic.

the themes, symbols, and meaning of the experiences were presented. Phenomenological research is based on two premises. The first was that experience was a valid, rich, and rewarding source of knowledge. According to Becker (1992), as cited in Morrissey Higgs (2006), stress that experience was described as a source of knowledge that shapes one's behavior. From the definition, human experience was viewed as a cornerstone of knowledge about human phenomena and not as an unreliable source. The second premise of phenomenological research lies in the view that the everyday world was a valuable and productive source of knowledge. By using phenomenology, which concerns the "what" and the "how" (Moustakas, 1995), the researcher hoped that the subjective experiences and perspectives of the participants would provide highlights as to how the program was implemented before COVID-19 and how it was currently executed.

the individual experiences of the teachers under the new normal in Philippine public education. There were ten (10) school heads as study participants who had firsthand experiences in the new normal in Philippine public education. The data gathered were recorded, transcribed, and validated to extract first-hand experiences on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats in the new normal in Philippine public education from the secondary teachers' lived experiences. A phenomenological research design used the Colaizzi method of data analysis. This is purely academic. The participants signed the informed consent form, and this study has no

risks. They can withdraw anytime as participants. Ethical considerations and safety health protocols were followed. Phenomenology is an approach to qualitative research that focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. The approach's fundamental goal was to describe the nature of the particular phenomenon (Creswell, 2013). Typically, interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. The interview(s) attempts to answer two broad questions (Moustakas, 1994): What have you experienced regarding the phenomenon? What contexts or situations have typically influenced your experiences of the phenomenon (Creswell, 2013)? Other forms of data, such as documents, observations, and art, may also be used. The data were then read, reread, and culled for phrases and themes that were then grouped to form clusters of meaning (Creswell, 2013). Through this process, the researcher may construct the universal meaning of the event, situation, or experience and arrive at a more profound understanding of the phenomenon. Some philosophical assumptions were employed in the development of research methodology. Subjective evidence gathered from field investigations was subject to epis-

temological assumptions dealing with subjective evidence. Subjective evidence collected from field studies has also been used to gain knowledge brought by the accessibility of the place. Axiological assumptions account for the researcher's biases and actively report them; they were used to determine whether the environment being investigated resulted from the behavior seen. Ontological assumptions refer to the nature of the reality of the subject being researched. The latter assumption was best suited to my study, for as a qualitative researcher, I believe that different individuals perceive these realities. I also believe that these realities were heavily shaped by their experiences. The phenomenological design interprets the experiences or facts, by listening to the experiences of the participants and providing the meaning of those experiences (Creswell, 2007). It describes the structures of experiences as they present themselves to consciousness, without recourse to theory, deduction, or Epistemology rhetoric assumption from other disciplines. The design examines the phenomena through the subjective eyes of the participants that describe the meaning of the experiences for several individuals about a concept or phenomenon (Creswell, 2007).

2.4. Research Participants—In the selection of the research participants, purposive sampling was applied. A sampling technique in which the researcher relies on his or her own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in the study. It was a non-probability sampling method, and it occurs when elements selected for the sample were chosen by the judgment of the researcher. Researchers often believe that they can obtain a

representative sample by using sound judgment, which would result in saving time and money (Black, 2010). In this study, suitable samples include teachers who were public school teachers, either male or female teacher, in Baracayo Integrated School in the Division of Davao City. There were ten (10) informants who were part of the in-depth interview. Moreover, to protect the identity of the participants, coding was used. IDI-FT1 to IDI-FT7 were used for the informants of the in-depth interview.

2.5. Ethical Considerations—

Creswell (2007) emphasized that qualitative researchers face many ethical issues that surface during data collection in the field and analysis and dissemination of qualitative reports. In this study, the researcher would deal with public school teachers, at Baracayo Integrated School. To ensure an authentic response from the participants, the researcher was responsible for exercising extra caution and maintaining the confidentiality of the study. The rights of the participants were highly considered. Besides, they would not be forced to be part of the study when they refused. In protecting the identity of the participants, Glesne and Peshkins (1992) suggested that providing and assigning numbers or aliases can protect the anonymity of the participants. In this study, I used codes to protect the identity of the participants. Added to this, as the researcher, I explained the purpose and significance of the study. The participants were given the chance to question the researcher about the nature of the study. This certifies that the information is clear to the participants. Moreover, the data gathering and the participation of the participants are guided by the Informed Consent Form, which is signed by the chosen participants. Lastly, the results and findings were presented back to the participants for verification. The transcriptions of the recorded interview were kept private. Further, each participant was advised that they have the right to withdraw their information at any time up to the completion of the data collection process and that they can be requested and allowed to verify their transcript after the interview is carried out. This would provide the participants with the opportunity to amend or remove any information that they feel might identify them. The researcher would reserve the right to use pseudonyms and change names and/or non-significant dates to protect the participant's identity in all subsequent data analysis and reporting. Qualification of the Researcher. The researcher would ensure that he or she possesses the needed qualifications to conduct the study. The researcher should have completed the academic requirements and passed the comprehensive examination before thesis writing, which was the last requirement to obtain the master's degree. The researcher should also be qualified to conduct the study physically, mentally, emotionally, and financially. In addition, the advisee-adviser tandem ensured that the study would reach its completion. Adequacy of Facilities. The researcher would strive to complete the study successfully at the specified time and that he or she was equipped with the necessary resources. Likewise, the technical committee would help enhance the paper by giving the needed suggestions and recommendations. Also, the researcher would ensure that he or she has enough funds to continue and finish the research. Thus, this study was hoped to be completed at the target time. Community Involvement. The researcher showed respect for the local traditions, culture, and views of the respondents in this study. Moreover, this study would not use deceit in any stage of its implementation, specifically in recruiting the participants or data collection methods. Furthermore, the researcher would necessarily express great pleasure in the wholehearted participation of the interviewees in the conduct of the study. Plagiarism and Fabrication as the researcher. The researcher would respect other works by properly citing the author and rewriting what someone else has said his or her way. The researcher would also always use quotes to indicate that the text has been taken from another paper. Similarly, the researcher would ensure that honesty was present in working on the manuscript and that no intentional misrepresentation and making up of data and or results were included, or purposefully putting forward conclusions that were not accurate

2.6. *Role of the Researcher—*

In this study, I used an Interview Guide Question Tool with sub-questions for the in-depth online interview. The tool was used as my guide while interviewing the selected teachers who were my participants in the recorded, in-depth online interview. This aimed to answer the research questions and collect additional inputs that could be useful in my study. To address the validity issues of this design, specifically the method, I would ask for help from the experts. The experts checked and validated my interview guide question tool. The sampling that was used for the selection of my participants was based on the suggestions of the expert panels. In identifying these research informants, there were ten (10) public school teachers, either male or female teachers, at Baracayo Integrated School, Cluster 5, Davao City Division. Purposive sampling was used, especially exemplified through

2.7. Data Collection—According to Creswell (2013), an important step in the process was to find people or places to study and to gain access to and establish rapport with participants so that they would provide good data. A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as interviews or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called “field issues,” which may be a problem, such as having inadequate data, needing to prematurely leave the field or site, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she will store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In gathering data, strict compliance with IATF protocols was

the key informant technique wherein one or a few individuals are solicited to act as guides to a culture (Tongco, 2007). I used a referral system so that I could be able to access teachers who would help qualify my criteria. This system is also called snowball sampling. Snowball sampling was a non-probability-based sampling technique that was used to gain access to such populations. The participants were purposely chosen so that the information needed could expedite the study. However, the application of snowball sampling was later appropriated to gather the exact data needed to answer the research questions. Moreover, the identity of my participants was strictly valued and respected under the “ethics of research.” Hence, the researcher’s interaction with them was collegial and morally upright.

observed. The researcher secured a permission letter to the participants and sent it via email. Upon approval, the researcher used the data collection forms as prescribed in the qualitative design. In this study, recording an in-depth interview and focus group discussion have been used. The researcher needs to get the subjective interaction between the study participants. The researcher heavily relied on naturalistic methods (interviewing and audio-recording), and the interpretive paradigm was used. Interpretive approaches rely heavily on naturalistic methods like interviewing and observation and analysis of existing texts. These methods ensure an adequate dialog between the researchers and those with whom they interact to collaboratively construct a meaningful reality. Yin, as cited by Aquilam (2014), suggested numerous forms of data collection, including documents, archival records, interviews, direct observation, participant observation, and physical artifacts. To have legitimate and trustworthy data on teachers’ experiences of the new normal way of

teaching and learning, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion. The interview aimed to gather information on the feelings and experiences of teachers. The participants have been encouraged to express their answers in their most comfortable manner. The interview with the participants has been transcribed word for word. Lastly, the researcher analyzed the data collected using discourse analysis and thematic analysis. Creswell (2007) suggested that succeeding in the conduct of the study, the data must be stored so that they can easily be found and protected from damage and loss. Furthermore, Interviews has also strengths and weaknesses. One of the strengths of an interview is that the interviews provide useful information when participants

cannot be directly observed. The interviewer has better control over the types of information that they receive. They could also pick their questions. If worded effectively, questions would encourage unbiased and truthful answers. However, one of the weaknesses was that the interviewee may provide biased information or be unreliable if only one interviewer is interpreting the information. The best research requires many different points of view. The answers may be deceptive because the interviewee tries to respond in a way that would please the interviewer. Then, equipment may be costly and require a high level of technical competence to be used, and it can be time-consuming. Inexperienced interviewers may not be able to keep the questions properly focused (Quad, 2016).

2.8. Data Analysis—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a full description of her experience of the phenomenon. This was an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus could be directed to the participants. She developed a list of significant statements. She then finds statements about how individuals were experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of no repetitive, no over-

lapping statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger information units, called "meaning units" or themes. She wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. It was called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, she wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study.

2.9. Framework of Analysis—Braun and Clark (2006) state that qualitative data analysis methods fall into two groups. The first group consists of methods driven by an epistemological or theoretical position, which have limited variability in how they are applied within their frameworks, such as conversation analysis (CA) and interpretative phenomenological analysis

(IPA) and methods that were situated within a broad theoretical framework and can therefore be used in a variety of ways within those frameworks, such as grounded theory (GT), discourse analysis (DA) narrative analysis (NA). The second group includes methods independent of theory and epistemology, which can be applied across various theoretical and episte-

mological approaches and are, therefore, very flexible. One such method is thematic analysis, which, through theoretical freedom, “provides flexible and valuable research tool, potentially providing a rich, detailed, yet complex account of data (Braun Clark, 2006). I observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my resources to transcribe using my computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing conventions with transcribers. Some negotiated themselves to lay out the conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step was data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. I used the-

matic grids and charts, the framework technique developed by the National Centre for Social Research (Ritchie et al, 2003). This technique was helpful to me in coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was instrumental in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps. To summarize, the thematic analysis method outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006) consisted of six (6) phases used in analyzing the data. Phase 1. I familiarized myself with the data by reading the whole data set and noting down initial ideas; Phase 2. I generated initial codes, with code being the most essential segment of the raw data that can identify a feature of the data that appears attractive; Phase 3. I searched for themes by sorting different codes into potential themes and collated all data extracts within identified themes; Phase 4. I reviewed the themes and refined them further (at the level of coded data extracts and the entire data set) and produced a thematic map showing relationships between themes and sub-themes; Phase 5. I defined and named themes, ensuring they give the reader an immediate sense of what the theme is all about. Phase 6. I wrote the report to convince the reader of the merit and validity of the analysis (within and across the themes). I used data extracts embedded within an analytic narrative to make arguments about the research question.

2.10. Trustworthiness of the Study—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the result and finding of the research study would depend on the process of how it is being conducted by the researcher. The

trustworthiness of a research study is important to evaluate its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness makes the researcher’s study worthy to read, share, and be proud of. The concepts of validity and reliability are relatively foreign to the field of qualitative

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

research. Instead of focusing on reliability and validity, qualitative researchers substitute data trustworthiness. Trustworthiness consists of the following components: credibility, transferability, dependability, and conformability (Harts, 2016). Credibility contributes to a belief in the trustworthiness of data by observing the attributes of prolonged engagement. To address the issue of credibility, interviewed as many research participants as possible or up to the point of saturation. Transferability is concerned with the extent to which the findings of one study can be applied to other situations. In positivist work, the concern often lies in demonstrating that the results of the work at hand can be applied to a wider population since the findings of a qualitative project are specific to a small number of particular environments and individuals. It is impossible to demonstrate that the findings and conclusions apply to other situations and populations. Therefore, to ensure transferability, I acknowledged that it is my responsi-

bility as a researcher to ensure that sufficient contextual transformation about the fieldwork sites is provided to enable the reader to make such a transfer. Confirmability associates objectivity in science with using instruments that are not dependent on human skill and perception. It is, however, difficult to ensure real objectivity since, as even tests and questionnaires are designed by humans, the intrusion of the researcher's biases is inevitable. Here, steps must be taken to help ensure as far as possible that the work's findings are the result of the experiences and ideas of the participants, rather than the characteristics and preferences of the researcher. Dependability involves the participants' evaluation of the findings, interpretation, and recommendations of the study, which are all supported by the data received from the participants of the study. Confirmability is the degree to which the findings of the research study could be confirmed by other researchers.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the analysis of the interview data. It presents themes that emerged from the analysis. Along with the themes, comprehensive discussions that answered the objectives of the study are presented. Before I began my discussion, I established the symbols I used to present the quotations based on the responses of the study participants. I used pseudonyms to refer to participants in the research, referring to the transcriptions of the interviews.

3.1. Experiences of Teachers in the New Normal Face-to-Face Classes—The first objective of this study is to explore the teachers' ex-

periences in the new normal. The interviews conducted revealed several themes. First, the teachers' workload increased. The next one was the difficulty in assessing students' progress.

3.1.1. Increase Workload—The first theme under the experiences of teachers in the new normal is the concern of the increasing workload of the teachers. With the need for more cleaning and sanitation, the teachers need to ensure that their classrooms are safe and following the IATF protocols. They will also create new les-

son plan or modify existing ones to the new classroom environment. From the statements of the participants above, they shared that one of the experiences of the teachers in the new normal is the increasing workload of the teachers. They shared how the teachers are always concerned about the health and sanitation of the

students. Teachers saddled with an excessive workload early in their careers are more likely to have their positive classroom management methods derailed, a recent study has revealed. The study, which followed 395 teachers from the start of their teaching education until 15 years into their teaching careers, also found that young, overworked teachers often resort to negative approaches in managing student misbehavior, including yelling and using sarcasm. In contrast, teachers who feel well-prepared and confident in their ability to manage classroom behavior are more likely to provide students with clear structure and expectations on how to conduct themselves in school. “This shows that teacher education isn’t just important in equipping future teachers with effective classroom management skills,” said Professor Helen Watt of the University of Sydney, one of the study’s three authors. “It’s also important to develop their confidence to manage student misbehavior through positive structures rather than negative reactions. But this gets derailed when teachers who are just becoming established are overwhelmed by paperwork and suffer extreme time pressure,” she said. Professor Watt also said

3.1.2. Changes to Classroom Dynamics— The second theme under the experiences of teachers in the new normal was concern about changes to classroom dynamics. The participants shared that teachers share about how to set up the classroom in a new normal. The statements the participants above shared about the teacher’s painting skills. The adoption of the new teaching strategies is one of the vital roles. The debate on art education programs has been increasingly examined since the No Child Left Behind Act of 2001. The No Child Left Behind Act is a standards-based education reform, which requires states to create assessments and test each school to make sure that students are receiving adequate schooling. In the book *Many Children Left Behind* by Meier et al. (2004),

that teachers’ classroom management methods confidence, and professional preparedness are “established fairly early” and likely to persist into their mid-careers. The way teachers start sets up long-term professional behaviors,” she said. “The key message from our findings is that the excessive demands experienced by beginning teachers have long-term, damaging consequences in their teaching behavior. Teachers’ workload is associated with practical classroom teaching and learning. The amount of teachers’ workload determines the academic performance of the school. Primary school teachers’ workload is challenging for effective classroom teaching and learning. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to study the teachers’ workload of primary school teachers in Punakha dzongkhag. The study involved potential additional work areas that burden primary school teachers. During the traditional mode of classes prior to the pandemic, the students had more control over their daily and weekly schedules, allowing them to allot time for self-care activities. However, during the pandemic, most of their time had been eaten by schoolwork.

they write: “We continue to confuse test scores with quality schooling, even though there is no evidence that high scores on these tests predict anything about a child’s success in life after school” (p. xii). The goal is to make each school accountable for the education the students are receiving through statewide standardized testing. Although this sounds good theoretically, it has also had several negative repercussions within schools. Assessment requirements have lead educators to devalue subjects that are not tested such as music and art. Meier et al (2004) write: “As non-tested areas (art, music, social studies) and ‘frills’ (field trips, naps, even recess) are eliminated, the school experience becomes limited, and everyone – children, parents and communities – reports less satisfaction with

the school” (p. xii). These programs tend to be replaced by test preparation time or more time spent in the tested subjects such as math and reading, because schools must meet state requirements in order to receive federal funding. As a result of economic constraints and the No Child Left Behind Act of 2001, schools are forced to make decisions on where to cut budget costs. It is not surprising that the increased focus on core subjects has resulted in schools deciding to cut art programs. Joseph Van Harken (2020) writes: “An unintended consequence is that the art and other classes like music, gym, science, and social studies get cut or compromised to make the budget focus more on the core curriculum” (2003). Many teachers and schools are encouraged to do whatever it takes to raise test scores, even if it means cutting out some of the more enjoyable aspects of education. However, there has also been a great deal of research on the benefits that the arts can provide to students. A report compiled from seven different studies called Champions of Change provides evidence as to how and why the arts enhance learning and achievement for students. After looking over the data, the Champions of Change researchers found that “while learning in other disciplines may often focus on the development of a single skill or talent, the arts regularly engage multiple skills and abilities” (Jack, 2009). This helps students develop into well-rounded learners. Additionally, the researchers found that “the arts transform the environment for learning. . . the very school culture is changed and the conditions for learning are improved. Figurative walls between classrooms and disciplines are broken down. Therefore, a welltaught arts program goes beyond just teaching about the arts and really transforms the learning environment. These researchers also found that the arts might provide a reason for students at risk of dropping out of school to stay in school. This is because the arts can engage students in a way that more traditional classes may not be. Furthermore “success in the arts became a bridge to learning and eventual success in other areas of learning. They found that arts might provide this success for any student, although especially for those who are considered low achieving in other classes. Finally, they found that the arts connect students to each other while helping students to take risks. One study by James Catterall, Richard Chapleau, and John Iwanaga (2020) found three main observations about the arts and academics. First, they found that “positive developments for children engaged in the arts are seen at each step in the research. They found that these positive developments also held true for children from low-income families. Secondly, they concluded that “students who report consistently high levels of involvement in instrumental music over the middle and high school years show significantly higher levels of mathematics proficiency by grade 12. Their final conclusion was that student involvement in theatre arts is associated with better reading abilities, gains in motivation and confidence as well as more tolerance for others (Catterall, Chaplea 2020). These findings are all important because one of the main reasons for cutting art programs out of schools is to improve performance in core classes, yet this research shows that the arts can help to improve those scores (Van Harken, 2003). Jerome Kagan (2009) as well as several others (Eisner, 2014) argues several reasons as to why the arts are important in elementary education. Kagan (2009) wrote that “the arts boost the self-confidence of children who are behind in mastery of reading and arithmetic. . . children, like adults, are vulnerable to becoming discouraged when they sense that a goal they desire is probably unattainable. . . one strategy to mute a child’s discouraging evaluation of self-competence is to provide the child with opportunities to be successful at some classroom task. This boost in confidence can then be generalized to other academic domains. Kagan (2009) also argues,

Fig. 3. Experiences of Teachers in the New Normal Face-to-Face Classes

“the arts and music provide an opportunity to persuade children that investing effort to create an object of beauty is an ideal worthy of celebration. Making beauty has an advantage over obtaining ‘A’ grades because others can share in the enjoyment of a beautiful product; only the self enjoys high grades. He also reports that an advantage of the arts is that they encourage students to work together as a group and focus on each other instead of the focus on individual work, which is typical of academic classes (Kagan, 2009). Work in the arts is not only a way of creating performances and products; it is a way of creating our lives by expanding our consciousness, shaping our dispositions, satisfying our quest for meaning, establishing contact with others, and sharing a culture” (Eisner, 2004). These are all skills that are much less likely to be attained from other academic classes. Furthermore, he writes: “Education. . . is the process of learning to create ourselves, and it is what the arts, both as a process and as the fruits of that process, promote” (Eisner, 2004). The arts teach many lessons that are not likely learned in the classroom environment created by more

traditional classes. Much of traditional learning has to do with following rules and coming up with the right answer. Therefore, the arts are important to open the students’ minds up to other possibilities and ways of thinking. The majority of art education research has been on whether or not it is beneficial and valuable for students, especially when schools must pass standardized tests and face budget costs. However, there seems to be a hole in the research. I have not found much research that compares what exactly goes on in art classrooms that enables a different type of learning and encourages different types of skills and abilities. There is a possibility that less the arts make a difference but more the type of environment created. This is important to research seven because there is a possibility that these benefits can be experienced in any classroom by changing the classroom dynamics and teacher intentions instead of changing the content. Figure 3 shows teachers’ experiences in the new normal of face-to-face classes. The emergence of the two themes is Increased Workload and Changed classroom dynamics.

3.2. *Coping Mechanism with the Challenges Encountered during the face-to-face*—Another study objective is to explore the different coping mechanisms teachers may experience in the new normal. In the interviews, the teachers shared that the coping mechanisms they employ are self-care and empathy.

3.2.1. *Self-care*—Many teachers have prioritized self-care as a way to manage stress and anxiety. This includes exercise, meditation, sleeping well, and taking breaks when needed. They have shared that being able to care for oneself is also one way of easing mental health concerns. Teachers play a central role in creating a classroom climate that fosters student learning and social-emotional well-being. However, teaching can be stressful, and managing classroom dynamics is taxing. As a profession, teaching is plagued by significant turnover, often attributed to burnout, with documented rates of teacher turnover rising in public schools over the past decade (Ingersoll, 2001; NCES, 2011). For teachers who stay, stress can impact their ability to be responsive and effective in the classroom. Multiple sources of stress have been cited including time demands, workload, student disruptive behavior, and organizational factors (Blase, 2016; Boyle, 2015). Teachers also face increasing pressure and scrutiny with accountability to standardized tests. While these issues are complex and have a long history, effectively addressing and supporting teachers in the current climate will require teacher involvement (Farber, 2011). The personal, societal, and financial costs associated with burnout are too high to ignore. Teachers' perceptions of stress and their ability to cope with demands are implicated in burnout (McCormick Barnett, 2011). In particular, a sense of self-efficacy and connectedness with students and colleagues have been identified as important elements linked to teaching engagement and less emotional exhaustion and psychological distress (Klassen et al., 2012; Tuettemann Punch, 1992). Teacher stress and burnout have been an ongoing challenge in education. Providing resources to increase teachers' sense of personal efficacy and ability to manage stress may reduce burnout. Reducing and managing teacher stress is part of promoting a healthy classroom environment. Retaining teachers and providing them with tools for self-care can translate into increased effectiveness in their role in the classroom. Supporting teachers' ability to cope with classroom demands and bolstering their well-being is necessary, with implications for students' learning and school success. Most school-based interventions are designed for students. There are fewer efforts to address stress and burnout among teachers and boost teacher well-being. Programs geared toward teachers are varied in scope and have been met with varying degrees of success (Richardson Rothstein, 2008). However, a program systematically implemented as part of professional training for teachers remains to be implemented. More needs to be done to address and support teachers in meeting the continuously shifting demands of the classroom. Mindfulness training to target attention and emotion processing is an approach to stress reduction that has gained increasing recognition (Bishop et al., 2004). Used across a variety of settings, Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR; Kabat-Zinn, 1990) is a widely known form of mindfulness training that has been shown to reduce stress, depression, and anxiety (Grossman et al., 2004; Hofmann et al., 2010). These mental health concerns are frequently reported among educators (Kyriacou, 2001). Therefore, teachers may derive benefit from learning and practicing mindfulness techniques. However, given considerable workload demands, often juggled with family responsibilities, teachers may not seek out such training from a health care provider. Therefore, making training read-

ily accessible and specifically relevant to educators outside of a strictly mental health care framework are important considerations. Our goal was to conduct a preliminary evaluation of a modified Mindfulness Based Stress Reduction (mMBSR) training specifically adapted for elementary school teachers. Mindfulness training enhances attention by bringing awareness to the object of attention whether it is the breath, other bodily sensations, external stimuli, thoughts or emotions. Training may increase the ability to sustain engagement of self-regulatory neural circuits in the prefrontal cortex resulting in improved sustained attention and emotion regulation (Lutz, Slatger, Dunne, Davidson, 2008) as well as alterations in functional connectivity of brain networks associated with attentional focus and reflective awareness of sensory experience (Kilpatrick et al., 2011). In mindfulness, attention can be deployed flexibly either in a narrow, focused way or broadly, to encompass a range of stimuli. From these practices, a greater awareness of sensory experiences may arise. Training attention also enables the deliberate cultivation of positive qualities through specific practices designed to promote empathy and prosocial attitudes. This form of mental training is associated with increased activity in cortical areas responsible for empathy and compassion (Lutz et al., 2008). Mindfulness may make individuals less reactive to negative experiences and more

likely to notice positive experiences, resulting in a cascade of psychological and physiological benefits. Approaches to stress management interventions may operate at different levels by targeting either the intensity of stress at work, perceptions or appraisals of stressful situations, and/or ways of coping with stress (Richardson Rothstein, 2008). Mindfulness is likely to act on the latter two aspects, that is, perceptions of stress and coping with stress. Mindfulness does not directly act on the target of stress, though a shift in perception and response to stressors could conceivably alter the nature of the stressor itself. In this respect, mindfulness shares similarities with other approaches that have been successfully used to reduce workplace stress, like cognitive re-framing, but it also has distinct differences. Whereas a main ingredient of cognitive behavioral approaches involves replacing “maladaptive beliefs” with constructive, positive beliefs, a key difference with mindfulness is that it entails observing and noticing without reacting to or intentionally altering direct experience in the moment (Segal, Williams, Teasdale, 2002). Certain practices are also specifically designed to cultivate an appreciation for and understanding of our interdependence with the world. A mindful approach to stress may involve noticing body sensations, observing thoughts and emotions related to stress, and practicing self-compassion.

3.2.2. *Being empathetic*—One of the coping mechanisms that teachers employ to address their challenges in new normal is being empathetic. They have shared that being able to put their shoes on what their students feel has enabled them to offer sound advice that helped the students ease their mental health concerns. In their statements above, the participants shared one of the coping mechanisms that they employ to address their challenges in the new normal. They shared that through empathy, they are able

to give advice and adjust schedules to ease the mental health of the students. People need support and understanding (empathy) in all life aspects—even at work (Edmondson Lei, 2014). Outside of work, family and friends provide support. At work, a person can turn to coworkers and colleagues. But leaders can give empathy as well. By doing so, leaders create a powerful bond that encourages and sustains followers in endeavors needed to improve workplace performance (Holt Marques, 2012). Empathy—the

ability to understand and appreciate another person's experiences while providing emotional support and a feeling of security (Mahsud et al., 2010)—increases job satisfaction and feelings of security that support people trying innovative ways to accomplish daily tasks (Mahsud et al., 2010). Empathy is a construct that is fundamental to leadership. Many leadership theories suggest the ability to have and display empathy is an important part of leadership. Transformational leaders need empathy in order to show their followers that they care for their needs and achievements. Authentic leaders also need empathy to be aware of others (Walumbwa et al., 2008). Empathy is also crucial to emotional intelligence, which several researchers believe is critical to being an effective leader (Salovey Mayer, 2014). Concurrent to this, qualitative studies conducted in U.K. schools suggested that school leaders' empathic abilities were valuable in changing schools' emotionally charged situation, e.g., in the social justice transformation process (Cliffe, 2011; Crawford, 2004). Similarly, Jansen (2006) found that school leaders' empathy allowed themselves to "touch others and be touched", thus became the viable force to balance, make the change, and enable transformation in the mostly unsupportive environment. Principals' effectiveness in dealing with complaints in the interaction between principals and parents was examined in a mixed-methods study (Robinson Le Fevre, 2011). It was found that those who demonstrated a deeper level of interest in parents' emotions were perceived as more respectful. These studies highlight the value of empathy in implementing effective communication in the school administration. Furthermore, research also examined whether professional development that targets raising leaders' awareness of empathic abilities could help school management. Parish (2015) conducted interviews before and after a leadership capacity development intervention and found empathy (understanding oth-

ers and taking an active interest in their concerns) was identified as the most significant emotional intelligence trait. The participants considered empathy as "the need for leaders to accurately identify and understand a person, their concerns, needs, and abilities and then appropriately manage the person in light of this understanding to promote productivity and success." Meanwhile, several quantitative studies examining whether leaders' empathic abilities could be enhanced with interventions or training programs provided mixed results (Semel, 2016). Even though empathy has attracted attention in the field of educational leadership (Zorn Bolder, 2007), there is hardly any consensus on what construct it truly means. Even when research adopted almost identical definitions of empathy, the empirical studies tend to vary significantly in their operational definitions. Furthermore, these studies typically show associations between empathy and leadership behavior instead of causal relationships and tend to be low-power studies with a small sample size. Thus, it is hard to translate into specific action recommendations. For example, this could lead to discrepancies in what researchers conceptualized and what leaders on the ground perceived and operated. Fortunately, research has shown significant progress in understanding empathy in recent years. In the section below, we will discuss the recent research on empathy and make conjecture to its relevance to the educational leadership setting. A number of authors have emphasized the importance of empathy, described as the ability to understand the perspectives of others (Combs et al., 2018), in crisis leadership. DuBrin (2013) discusses leaders drawing on their emotional intelligence including empathy and compassion in times of crisis, and Kerrissey and Edmonson (2020) highlight the importance of leaders making themselves 'available to feel what it is like to be in another's shoes'. Similarly, Koehn (2020), writing specifically about leading through COVID-19, sug-

gests that leaders explain that they understand how scared people may be and provide a way forward by giving them purpose and direction. Leading with empathy facilitates the building of trusting relationships (Combs et al., 2018) and trust is particularly important in crisis leadership as decisions are more likely to be accepted when stakeholders have trust and confidence in the leader's direction (DuBrin, 2013; Schoenberg, 2005; Wooten James, 2008; Wooten et al., 2013). Trust may also result in more rapid adaptation in times of crisis, thereby enhancing organizational resilience (Teo et al., 2017). While effective communication is important for all leaders, it becomes more urgent in times of crisis. It needs to be iterative and transparent (Kerrissey Edmondson, 2020), as well as extensive and honest (DuBrin, 2013). Smith and Riley (2012) suggest that communication is 'the key attribute through which the leader can provide direction, certainty, and optimism during a crisis' and advocate for two-way communication. Schoenberg (2005) has emphasized the role of a crisis leader as the spokesperson who must constantly communicate news and updates to target audiences. According to Boin et al. (2013), communication should 'explain the crisis, its consequences, what is being done to minimize the consequences. It should also offer "actionable advice", explaining what should be

done, by whom, and why.' Pang et al. (2013) argue that leaders need to have an understanding of the emotions of their stakeholders and tailor their communication strategies accordingly. These authors also promote leaders instigating personal or small-group contact to help people cope with their emotions. Effective crisis leaders need to be comfortable with ambiguity and disorder and must adjust and improvise, acknowledging that mistakes will be made and learning needs to be ongoing (Koehn, 2020). Koehn (2020) also highlights the COVID-19 crisis as a powerful opportunity for organizations and teams of all kinds to understand their weaknesses better, what engages and motivates their people, and their reason for being. The importance of making rapid adjustments in direction or pivoting in response to COVID-19 and being prepared to learn has also been stressed (Johnson Suskewicz, 2020). Earlier research also highlighted the importance of crisis leaders being adaptable and flexible and taking opportunities that crises create to make changes (DuBrin, 2013; Smith Riley, 2012). This ability to capitalize on opportunities can involve learning during and after crises (Deverell, 2011). Figure 4 shows the Coping Mechanism with the Challenges Encountered during the New Normal face-to-face classes. The emergence of the two themes is Self-care and Being Empathetic.

3.3. Educational Management Insights drawn from the Findings of the Study—Teachers and students may suffer due to a lack of wellness initiatives. It affects students' academic performance since teachers cannot offer their all in the teaching-learning process (Khan et al., 2012; Swathi Reddy, 2015). As a result, a wellness program is critical to offering high-quality education. Being free of any sickness, illness, or disease means living in a stress-free atmosphere. It is the best strategy to promote good health and increase the quality of life in the commu-

nity (Edlin Golanty, 2010). Stress-free signifies "wellness," or the absence of any illnesses or diseases. The concern for the mental health of teachers has been heightened due to the challenges brought about by the pandemic. As we have transitioned from one modality to new modalities, it has been a challenge for teachers physically and mentally. For this, one of the stakeholders that plays an important role in supporting the mental health of teachers during this new normal, are the school principals as they are ones who take the managerial role in

Fig. 4. Coping Mechanism with the Challenges Encountered during the Face to Face schools. The fundamental goal of a wellness program for teachers is to make them physically fit and healthy (Kipps-Vaughn, Ponsart Gilligan, 2012). This signifies that the program’s teachers would follow the technique to improve their health. The school principals are in charge of launching the wellness program because instructors are under the supervision of school leaders or principals. They should plan, administer, and manage their school’s wellness program. Teachers can perform at their best in their field of work with the support of a wellness program. To make this happen, teachers play a critical role in ensuring that students’ needs are met. Furthermore, they are responsible for looking after of the welfare of the students in an empathetic way. Many studies (Royal, Flammer, Borst, Huckle, Barter Neel, 2016; Swarbrick, D’Antonio Nemeč, 2011; and Anenson, Brunt, Terbizan Christensen, 2013) proved the importance of a wellness program in the school community. Only a few schools, mainly in Metro Manila, Philippines, offer such programs. According to Abanto (2019), concerns related to equipment and fiscal allocation hinder the success of the program. From the results of this study, the teachers have experienced their students being always concerned about their health and their families’, due to the health risks brought by the covid-19 pandemic. They have also shared that the teachers have been also concerned about being mentally strained and burnt out because of simultaneous programs and meetings conducted online. Furthermore, they have shared that one of their challenges is that they are not always equipped with knowledge on how to deal with the mental health problems of teachers, especially when their concerns are already too emotional. From the school principals’ experiences in supporting the teachers’ mental health during the new normal, several educational insights can be had. The first one is that school principals are being looked at by the teachers not just as managers for the different tasks in schools but also as people with whom they can share their problems. Given the challenges that many teachers face during the pandemic, it is important for them to have someone with whom they can share their problems, and in this case, it will be the school principals. Another insight that can be had is great importance for school principals to be able to handle the heightened emotions and worries of teachers because of the health risks imposed by the

pandemic. This highlights the importance of the quality of principals' leadership in terms of emotional factors so that they can provide adequate and appropriate guidance to teachers during the new normal. This further highlights the importance of collaboration and companionship among teachers and school principals to reduce mental challenges brought on by the worries about health and the demands of distance learning modalities. Sunga (2019) investigated Fil-

ipino teachers' quality of life and mental health and advocated the creation of a wellness program to solve the problem. Similarly, human resource offices in Philippine schools should implement wellness programs with institutionalized incentives whenever staff maintain their physical fitness (Lope, 2019). Additionally, the wellness program may assist instructors in being more holistically fit and healthy.

4. Implications and Future Directions

This chapter presents a brief overview of the study, followed by implications based on its findings.

4.1. Findings—This study's main objective was to explore teachers' experiences in the new normal. Specifically, it sought to identify teachers' experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms as they face the new normal. For their experiences, the teachers have experienced increased workloads, with the need for more cleaning and sanitation, keeping their classrooms safe, and following the new guidelines. Teachers also create new lesson plans or modify existing ones to fit the new classroom environment. Another experience that the teachers had was the change in classroom dynamics. The new face-to-face classes may differ from what teachers are used to, and they may need to adjust to the new classroom dynamics. Teachers may

need to find new ways to engage with students and build rapport, particularly as they may feel anxious or uncertain. Under the coping mechanism, the teachers shared concerns about their health. The participants shared that teachers were constantly concerned about their health and their families because of the health risks imposed by the pandemic. They have prioritized self-care as a way to manage stress and anxiety, which includes exercise, meditation, getting enough sleep, and taking breaks when needed. The teacher also was empathetic to the concerns and conditions of the student. Part of the responsibilities of a teacher is to ensure that, as a teacher, you can understand your student's feelings.

4.2. Implications—The results of this study have several implications. Firstly, regarding the teachers' experiences in the New Normal, face-to-face classes that teachers had during the New Normal were challenging jobs for school principals, and subthemes revealed, such as increased workload. Firstly, the teachers' experiences in the New Normal Face-to-face classes that teachers had during the New Normal were challenging for school principals, and subthemes revealed such as increased workload. The teachers must ensure that their classrooms

are secure and adhere to IATF guidelines in light of the increased requirement for cleanliness and sanitation. Additionally, they would develop fresh lesson plans or adapt current ones to the brand-new learning environment. They shared how the teachers are always concerned about the health and sanitation of the students. Second, there are Changes to classroom dynamics. One of the most critical roles was adopting innovative teaching methods. Since the No Child Left Behind Act of 2001, the discussion surrounding art education programs has received

more attention. To ensure that students receive proper instruction, the No Child Left Behind Act, a standards-based education reform, requires states to develop assessments and evaluate every school. For the coping mechanisms, it was revealed that self-care was one of the concerns; many teachers have given self-care top priority as a strategy to deal with stress and anxiety. Exercise, meditation, adequate rest, and taking pauses when needed all fall under this category. They mentioned that one approach to reducing mental health concerns is by being able to take care of oneself. The second was being empathetic. They have explained how being able to put themselves in their student's situation has allowed them to provide wise counsel that has helped the kids' mental health worries

to fade. Not only do they have to deal with the usual school problems, but they also have to deal with teachers' heightened fear and emotions because of the health risks imposed by the COVID-19 virus and their additional workload. This highlights the importance of having the skills for school principals to deal with the challenges of the teachers' mental health. As the study participants shared that they had problems doing so, it implies a need to upskill school principals in handling such matters. Furthermore, the study's results further imply that collaboration between school principals is essential in the new normal as it provides ways for problem-solving within the school and supports teachers' mental health.

4.3. Future Directions—Managing a classroom and managing the students' emotions are two separate things. While it was the teacher's job to keep the classroom dynamic, the teacher is also responsible for the welfare of the students. The results of this study suggest that teachers should be flexible when changing the new normal. They should not only manage the classroom or update their teaching skills but also be empathetic to the needs of the students. School Principals may also do their part

to ensure the mental health of teachers during this challenging time. They should also implement interventions or activities that would help school principals improve their approach to supporting teachers' mental health in times of crisis. Lastly, as the participants of this study are localized, the experiences of other teachers in another setting may be different. For this, there was a need to conduct research in a broader scope of participants to make data more generalizable.

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